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"HISTORY OF CULTURAL RELATION BETWEEN INDIA AND IRAN"

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Abstract

The relationship between India and Iran is from the Ancient time. According to the documents and books of ancient time like 'Rughveda' and 'Avaesta' which is written in the century by Nurbhrust. There is no difference between Indian languages and Iranie. Langues Both languages and Iraine languages. Both the languages are similar the context of words and proverbs Avaesta' describes the God and Goddess in Iran religion like Indra, Vayu, Nastya etc. are similar to the description of the gods from the Indian vedas. They are Indra, Vayu, Varttaghan hi India where 'Rughveda' has importance in Indian culture. The 'Avaesta' is a famous religious book in laran in the both books.³

Introduction

Iran was recognized in ancient period as Persia, Iran is a Asian country. The boundaries of Iran are nearer to Russia. Afghanistan, Iraq and Turkistan. 1 The word Persia properly applied only to the ancient province of Iran. In a modern period. Iran, hi modern period. Iran is vast territory of 62800 square miles. The country which we call Persia is a state created at the end of 18th century by the Qujar Dynstary.²

The culture is well known in world and it is reached by all means to its zenith. The cultural characterizes of this country are poetry, Literature, Architecture and design also, hi this paper I would like to highlight on the design of the Iranian Art. The eyes of traveler will be attracted by designs of this country. We be attracted by design of this country. We can see the rugs. embroider fabrics, on the silver and brass work etc. Iranian design is special characterizes of the culture. It is distinctive & unique. The design of Iran to be found nowhere else in the world because it is highly developed, perfectly executed and laden with the veritavel sperate of a people.³

Persian Influence on India

There are some point showe's close relationship between India and Iran.

- ✓ In Samrat Ashoks period we have seen Iranian Impact on stambha, chakra and Icons
- ✓ From ancient age the India merchants bring there products for sale in Iran.
- ✓ The Iranian people thought Indian to shine stone.

The main economic source of this country is lanel revenu. Farming is the main business of this country. The major part of land of Iran is cultivated land Because of this economic backing from Ancient period to modern the country because progressive not in Asia, but in world also.

Trade relationship between India and Iran

From Neolithic period relation between India and Iran. The existence of several empires spanning both persia and northern India ensured the constant migration of people between the two regions and the spread and evolution of the Indo-Iranian language groups. As a consequence, the people of India and Iran share significant cultural, linguistic and ethnic characteristics.

The Iranian Art is richer. Because of the trade and foreign Invasion, Iran was always in the contact of world. The people of Iran accepted the art, the design in paintings from so many nation. Design means a cultural expression of Iranian people. The design and the culture of Iran represents a completeness, specialization a concentration & inspiration. The people attracted to the thing which is beautiful and they thing which is beautiful and they express this beauty in a fashion, design and in a painting also.⁶

Iranian design is decorative. The Persian rug has been prized from centuries through out the civilized world. The rugs with good design and decoration is found in throne rooms of monarhs also in houses of Christian worship. It is found in the homes of those people in Iran who in west in beauty. The variety of the design which is shown by craftsman is capable, wide & rich. One can visit Iranian shop and can examine the Iranian beauty and the design.

Some scholars believed the Islamic influences are responsible for the Ironic design. The artist expressed their art with the help of Idols, human and animal figures, flowers etc. While Islamic influence may have been an important contributing factory. Islam was not the source of this interest. In abstract design among the Iranians, the Islamic probation were generally ignored and Iranian artistes continued to depict flower, animals and even human figures in there rugs, miniatures, pottery and murals. Before the Islamic conquests the Persian artists had shown an special aptitude for design we can found some good examples of Iranian designs in the museum of Teheran.

From the ancient period of modern period there are community of the Iranian designs and the potteries and bronzes display are some unique examples. So many dynasties ruled this country from B.C. and in their successive age. The designs show increased. Attention to the design became more apparent after the Aryans. Even though the designs in Persia recognized as a perso - Aryans designs but not only the Aryans designs.

Conclusion

We can see Persian design&AffslnTajMalsal, which was made by Iranian Architecture Ustad Ahmad Lahouri. Designs of Taj Mahal is very beautiful and we cannot see this type of arts in the world, that why Taj Mahal is a "Wrld wonder"

In India other places such as 'GOLGIMAT in Bijapur, Pawan Chakki in Aurangabad, Humayun's Tomb in Delhi & Various mosque are good examples of Iranian Persian designs & Arts. Thus I have tried to high light on the cultural aspects of Iran.

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